

Survey of Tree Flora of Deola Tehsil Area of Nashik District, Maharashtra.

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Abstract: Survey of Tree species in Deola Tehsil Area of Nashik district was carried out during January to December 2024. Total 58 Angiosperms species belonging to 46 genera and 27 families recorded. Out of 27 families, 26 belong to Dicotyledons and 1 from Monocotyledons, which represents the dominance of Dicotyledons. The purpose of the study was to investigate the tree species diversity of Deola Tehsil Area. Therefore, present work was undertaken.

Key words: Tree Flora, Species, Deola Tehsil Area

Introduction

The Deola Tehsil is situated in northern part of Nashik district and lies between North latitude 20° 23'45" to 20° 25' 38" and East longitude 74° 07' 29" to 74° 21' 27" and is spread over an area of 577.46 sq.km. There are 50 villages in Deola Tehsil. As per the Census India 2011, Deola Tehsil has 28,865 households, population of 1, 44,522 of which 75306 are males and 69,216 are females. It is situated on the confluence of the rivers Kolti and Bhawdi. etc. is rich in flora. The temperature averages 26.5°C. In a year, the average rainfall is 690 mm. Many workers have carried study on Flora in India like Dalzell & Gibson (1861), Gamble (1956), Cooke (1967), Shah (1978), Almeida (1990), Singh and Karthikeyan (2000), Singh et al., (2001), Niraj Sharma (2002). In recent few years some of the research workers have contributed in this area and published some research papers (Nair, 1986; Khairnar, 2010; Gaikwad and Mali, 2012; Jadhav, 2016; Sonawane, 2020, Pawar; 2020; Sonawane & Ahire). The Deola forests are rich region with respect to species diversity. This region is under severe biotic pressure and conserving the Plant diversity is a challenging task. The purpose of the study was to investigate the tree species in Deola Tehsil Area.

Material and Methods

An extensive survey was carried out in Deola Tehsil Area in year 2024. Study work was concentrated to investigate tree species of Deola Tehsil Area. The plants were identified with the help of keys to families, genera and species provided in standard floras like Flora of Bombay Presidency (Cooke, 1967 Vol. I- III), Flora of Maharashtra State (Singh et al; 2001, Vol. II), (Singh & Karthikeyan, 2000, Vol. I), (Sharma et al, 2000, Vol. III), The Bombay Flora (Dalzell & Gibson, 1861); Forest Flora of Bombay Presidency and Sind (Talbot 1909-11 Vol. II), Flora of Nasik District (Lakshminarasimhan and Sharma, 1991), Nature Heals A Glossary of Selected Indigenous Medicinal Plants of India (Jayvir Anjaria, et al., 1997), relevant literature and expert opinions.

Enumeration

The tree species with their families, botanical name and local name/s, flowering and fruiting period are given in table 1.

Table No. 1. Tree Flora of Deola Tehsil Area of Nashik District, Maharashtra.

Sr. No.	Name of the Family	Botanical Name	Local Names	Flower Colour	Fl.& Fr. Period
DICOTYLEDONS					
1.	Magnoliaceae	<i>Magnolia grandiflora</i> L.	Kavthi Champha	White	April-Aug.
2.	Annonaceae	<i>Annona reticulate</i> L.	Ramphal	Greenish Yellow	July- Nov.
		<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Sitaphal	Green	March-Aug.
3.	Malvaceae	<i>Thespesia populnea</i> (L.) Soland. Ex Correa	Bhendi	Yellow	Oct. – June
4.	Bombaceae	<i>Adansonia digitata</i> L.	Gorakh chinch	White	May- Oct.
5.	Rutaceae	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> Corr.	Bel	Greenish white	April-May
		<i>Feronia limonia</i> Correa.	Kavath	Pale green	Feb.- March
6.	Simaroubaceae	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> , Roxb.	Maharukh	Greenish	Jan.-Feb.
7.	Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> Adr. Juss	Neem	white	March- May
		<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	Bakam	White	March- May
8.	Rhamnaceae	<i>Zizyphus jujuba</i> , Lamk.	Bor	Greenish Yellow	April- Oct.
		<i>Zizyphus rugose</i>	Ranbor	White	Dec.-Jan.
		<i>Zizyphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Wild.	Ghatbor	Greenish yellow	March-July
9.	Sapindaceae	<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i> Gaertn.	Ritha	Greenish White	July-Dec.
10.	Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Amba	Greenish yellow	Jan.- Feb.
		<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> Linn.	Bhilawa	Greenish white	May-Sept. Dec-March
11.	Moringaceae	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk	Shewga	White	Jan.- April
		<i>Moringa concanensis</i> Nimmo ex Dalzell & Gibson	Kattumuringa	Yellowish- white	Oct-March
12.	Fabaceae	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Palas	Orange red	February
		<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> Roxb.	Shisav	Yellowish- white	Aug.- Oct.
		<i>Erythrina variegata</i> L.	Pangara	Bright Red	Feb.- April
		<i>Gliricidia sepium</i> Stend.	Giripushpa, Undirmari	Pinkish white	Feb. - April
13.	Caesalpinaceae	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> Pierre.	Karanj	White	April-June
		<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> , Lam.	Aapta	White	May- Oct.
		<i>Cassia fistula</i> , L.	Bahava	Yellow	April- Oct.
		<i>Cassia simea</i> Lam.	Kassod	Yellow	Throughout the year
		<i>Delonix regia</i> , Rafi.	Gulmohar	Reddish orange	April – Sept.
14.	Mimosaceae	<i>Tamarindus indicus</i> , Linn	Chinch	Yellow	Feb.- June
		<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> A. cumm. Ex. B.	Australian babhul	Yellow	Aug.-March
		<i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.f) Wild.	Khair	Pale yellow	June- Oct.
		<i>Acacia indica</i> Beth.	Babhul	Yellow	July-Jan.
		<i>Acacia nilotica</i> Lam.	Ramkhati , Babhul	Yellow	July- Dec.
		<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L) Benth.	Siris	White	May
		<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> (L.) De. Wit.	Subabhul	cream	Sept.- Oct.

		<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Bth.	Vilayati chinch	Yellow white	Jan.- June
		<i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (Sw.) D.C	Vedibabhul	Pale yellow	Feb.- May
		<i>Samanea saman</i> (Jacq.) Merr.	Rain tree	Pink	March-July
15.	Combretaceae	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. Ex DC ex. Guill & Peer.	Dhamoda	Whitish yellow	March-Nov.
		<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb.) Wight & Arn.	Arjun Sadada	Pale yellow	May- June Jan-March
		<i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	Desi badam	Green to Red	Jan.- Feb. July- Aug.
		<i>Terminalia chebula</i> (Gaertn.) Retz.	Hirda	Pale Yellow-White	May-June July-Dec.
16.	Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill.	Nilgiri	White	Jan.- Feb.
		<i>Syzygium jambolana</i> Lamk.	Jambhul	Greenish white	May- Sept.
17.	Oleaceae	<i>Nyctanthes arbor tristis</i> L.	Parijatak	Orange	Aug.- Feb.
18.	Apocynaceae	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> (Roxb.) R. Br.	Kala-Kuda	White	March -June
19.	Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G. Forst.	Bokhar	White	March - May
20.	Bignoniaceae	<i>Spathodea campanulata</i> P. Beauv	Spathodea	Orange	July - March
21.	Verbenaceae	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.	Sagwan , Sag	Pale yellow	Nov.- Dec.
22.	Santalaceae	<i>Santalum album</i> , L.	Chandan	Purple brown	Feb.- April
23.	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Emblica officinalis</i> Gaertn.	Awala	Greenish yellow	March - May
24.	Ulmaceae	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> (Roxb.) Planch	Papdi	Brownish	Jan.- June
25.	Moraceae	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam.	Phanus	Yellowish green	Dec.-March, July- Aug.
		<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Banyan tree, Vad	Red	Nov.- Jan.
		<i>F. glomerata</i> Roxb.	Umber	Pale green	Feb.- June
		<i>F. religiosa</i> L.	Pipal	Dark purple	Oct.- Nov.
26.	Casurinaceae	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i> , Forst.	Suru	Greenish	Aug.- Nov.
MONOCOTYLEDONS					
27.	Arecaceae	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Palm	Yellow-White	Feb.-July
		<i>Cocus nucifera</i> L.	Naral	Greenish	Throughout year

Note: Fl. Flowering & Fr. Fruiting.

Result And Discussion

Total 58 Angiosperms species belonging to 46 genera and 27 families has been recorded. Out of 27 families, 26 belongs to Dicotyledones and 1 from Monocotyledons, which represents the dominance of Dicotyledons. This region is under severe biotic pressure and conserving the plant diversity is a challenging task. Various plant species are facing a constant threat due to deforestation and over exploitation. The indiscriminate exploration of forest resources, over grazing the indigenous species are under pressure and may be face threat of extinction in future. This research paper may help to identify species diversity and needs for conservation prioritization and also to pay special attention for conservation of species diversity of the study area.

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